

Preference Guided Multiobjective Bayesian Optimization with Aspiration and Reservation Levels: Supplementary Matertials

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1 Experiments

The experimental settings are the same as those in the main paper. To demonstrate that the proposed ARES and EHVI-AR perform well on problems with different numbers of objective functions, we consider three problems: Branin-Currin from BoTorch [1], which is a classic problem; ZCAT1 [3], which is a challenging problem; and RE4-7-1 (car side impact problem) [2], which is a real-world problem. These problems were run for 30, 200, and 100 evaluations, respectively, as convergence to the PF seems to have been reached. The source code is also available at <https://github.com/Maomao2molly/BO-related>.

1.1 Results of a priori MOBO with the proposed methods

As in the main paper, the overall performance is measured by the D-PHI and ARC-HV values. We consider different preference settings to test whether proposed ARES and EHVI-AR perform well in all cases, that is, when \mathbf{a} is unattainable and \mathbf{r} is attainable (Case 1), or when \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{r} are both attainable (Case 2) or both unattainable (Case 3). As shown in Table 1, the preference information is set to include three cases for each problem.

In Figures 1, 3 and 5, Columns 1 and 3 show boxplots of ARC-HV and D-PHI values, respectively, while Columns 2 and 4 show the mean and standard error of ARC-HV and D-PHI over evaluations, respectively. For each method,

Table 1: Preference information for problems in three cases

Branin-Currin	Aspiration point	Reservation point
Case 1	[-5, -2]	[-7, -4]
Case 2	[-10, -3]	[-15, -4]
Case 3	[5, 0]	[-10, -1]
ZCAT1	Aspiration point	Reservation point
Case 1	[0, 0, 0]	[-0.7, -2, -5]
Case 2	[-1, -1, -2]	[-1.5, -4, -5]
Case 3	[0, 0, 0]	[0.4, -1, -3]
RE4-7-1	Aspiration point	Reservation point
Case 1	[-16, -3, -10, 1]	[-35, -4.2, -12, -6]
Case 2	[-35, -5, -13, -11]	[-40, -6, -15, -13]
Case 3	[-20, -3, -11, 1.5]	[-30, -3.5, -11.5, 0.5]

a box represents the range between the first quartile and the third quartile, with the median marked inside. The whiskers show values within 1.5 times the interquartile range. Points beyond the whiskers are shown as outliers.

Figure 1: ARC-HV (first two columns) and D-PHI (last two columns) values over 20 runs on Branin-Currin problem under different preference settings.

For each problem, we analyze one representative case in detail. On the Branin-Currin problem, in Figure 1 (a), when \mathbf{a} is unattainable and \mathbf{r} is attainable, EHVI performs slightly worse than our proposed ARES and EHV-AR according to the indicator curves. According to the boxplots, MOBO using EHV-AR, EHVI and ARES show similar performance in terms of ARC-HV,

Figure 2: Final point sets on Branin-Currin problem, with the three columns (from left to right) showing points evaluated by MOBO using EHVI-AR, EHVI, and ARES.

while EHVI-AR achieves slightly better D-PHI values than EHVI and ARES.

The corresponding final point sets are shown in Figure 2 (a). All three non-dominated sets fully cover the region between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{r} , resulting in similarly large ARC-HV values. Considering points better than \mathbf{r} , point sets evaluated by EHVI-AR and EHVI fully cover the region dominating \mathbf{r} , while ARES mainly evaluates points between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{r} and receives fewer rewards from D-PHI. Compared with EHVI-AR, EHVI evaluates more points that are non-dominated to \mathbf{r} but have objective function values significantly worse than the reservation levels, leading to greater penalties. Therefore, EHVI-AR achieves the best D-PHI by balancing higher rewards with lower penalties.

Figure 3: ARC-HV (first two columns) and D-PHI (last two columns) values over 20 runs on ZCAT1 problem under different preference settings.

On the ZCAT problem, as shown in Figure 3 (b), when \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{r} are attainable, EHVI performs worse than EHVI-AR and ARES in terms of both D-PHI and ARC-HV, while EHVI-AR performs worse than ARES in terms of ARC-HV. The corresponding final point sets are shown in Figure 4 (b). Both EHVI-AR and ARES evaluate some points that dominate \mathbf{a} , whereas EHVI evaluates only a few such points. Compared with EHVI-AR, the points evaluated by ARES are denser and cover a wider region dominating \mathbf{a} , resulting in the best ARC-HV values, while EHVI-AR achieves better ARC-HV values than EHVI.

Considering the region dominating \mathbf{r} , EHVI-AR evaluates more points, whereas ARES evaluates fewer. Nevertheless, both methods cover almost the entire region, while EHVI does not. From this perspective, EHVI-AR obtains more rewards from D-PHI than ARES, and ARES outperforms EHVI. Since this region includes the region dominating \mathbf{a} , where ARES obtains more rewards from D-PHI than EHVI-AR, the overall D-PHI values of EHVI-AR and ARES are similar, and both are higher than that of EHVI.

Figure 4: Final point sets on ZCAT1 problem, with the three columns (from left to right) showing points evaluated by MOBO using EHVI-AR, EHVI, and ARES.

Figure 5: ARC-HV (first two columns) and D-PHI (last two columns) values over 20 runs on RE4-7-1 problem under different preference settings.

Figure 6: Final point sets on RE4-7-1 problem, with the three columns (from left to right) showing points evaluated by MOBO using EHVI-AR, EHVI, and ARES.

On the RE4-7-1 problem, as shown in Figure 3 (a), when \mathbf{a} is unattainable and \mathbf{r} is attainable, EHVI performs slightly worse than EHVI-AR in terms of ARC-HV, while EHVI-AR is inferior to ARES. In terms of D-PHI, EHVI-AR performs better than ARES, whereas ARES outperforms EHVI. The corresponding final point sets are shown in Figure 4 (a), where \mathbf{a} is represented by the red line at the top of the figure.

Observing the first and fourth objective functions, the points evaluated by EHVI-AR cover a widest range of objective function values above the reservation level. As a result, some points with slightly worse values than the reservation level in the second and third objectives are also evaluated. By contrast, ARES evaluates fewer such points, leading to a slightly narrower coverage than EHVI-AR. Nevertheless, both ARES and EHVI-AR cover a wider range of objective function values beyond the aspiration levels than EHVI and therefore receive higher rewards from D-PHI and ARC-HV.

In summary, MOBO using ARES typically achieves the highest ARC-HV, as it rewards points likely to contribute to regions with balanced trade-offs, namely the regions between \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{r} , dominating \mathbf{a} or dominated by \mathbf{r} , performing particularly well when part of the PF lies in these regions. By contrast, MOBO using EHVI-AR usually achieves the best D-PHI values, since it considers the distribution of all solutions and rewards those with objective function values potentially better than the reservation levels.

1.2 Illustrative use in an interactive setting

Similar to the main paper, we present an example of using MOBO with ARES and EHVI-AR in an interactive way on the BBOB-biobj F1 problem under different preference settings. The preference information used is in Table 2.

Table 2: Preference information used in the interactive way

BBOB-biobj F1	Aspiration point	Reservation point
Iteration 1	[250, 30]	[190, -40]
Iteration 2	[200, 10]	[200, 20]

Figure 7: Mean and standard error of indicator values over evaluations for the BBOB-biobj F1 problem across two iterations.

Figure 8: Final point sets for the BBOB-biobj F1 problem in two iterations, with columns (left to right) showing points evaluated by EHVI-AR, EHVI, and ARES.

In Figure 7, the band around the indicator curve represents the standard error, a wider band indicates less stable performance. The curves show that ARES and EHVI-AR more consistently evaluate points that comply with the preference information. Figure 8 presents the final point sets from the run whose ARC-HV is closest to the final mean over 20 runs. Overall, in a limited number of evaluations, points evaluated by EHVI were randomly distributed over parts of the PF while EHVI-AR and ARES tended to explore the PF according to provided preference information.

References

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